

URLLC in Next-Generation Wireless Networks: Current Progress and Open Challenges

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Abstract

Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) is a key enabler for many next-generation wireless network applications, including autonomous vehicles, industrial automation, and telemedicine. It is designed to meet stringent requirements of latency as low as one millisecond and reliability levels exceeding 99.999%. These characteristics make URLLC essential for mission-critical applications where delays or failures could result in severe consequences. This paper provides a comprehensive review of URLLC research, categorizing existing studies based on various URLLC applications. Additionally, we identify key challenges, including resource allocation, interference management, and the integration of emerging technologies like AI and edge computing. Open research problems of future wireless networks are discussed, providing potential directions for advancing URLLC capabilities. This paper serves as a detailed reference for researchers by highlighting state-of-the-art methodologies and emerging directions in URLLC.

Index Terms

URLLC, 6G wireless networks, eMBB, next-generation wireless networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of wireless communication has reached several important milestones, with the introduction of 5G technology marking a transformative step in expanding the capabilities of wireless networks. Among the three major service categories of 5G, Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC), and Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC), URLLC is particularly transformative due to its ability to support applications with exceptionally stringent latency and reliability requirements. URLLC aims to achieve end-to-end latency as low as one millisecond and reliability levels up to 99.9999%, which is crucial for a wide range of mission-critical applications [1]. For instance, in autonomous driving, URLLC facilitates real-time communication between vehicles and infrastructure to enable collision avoidance and precise navigation. In remote surgery applications, URLLC ensures that commands and feedback between surgeons and robotic instruments are transmitted without perceptible delays to maintain surgical precision. Similarly, in industrial automation, URLLC enables synchronous operation of robotics and machinery to improve efficiency and safety in complex manufacturing environments.

The stringent demands of URLLC necessitate innovations across multiple layers of the communication stack. At the physical layer, techniques such as enhanced modulation, coding schemes, and diversity methods are critical to meeting reliability standards. At the network level, approaches like network slicing and edge computing help prioritize URLLC traffic and ensure consistent performance even in high-load scenarios [2]. Additionally, Medium Access Control (MAC) protocols designed to support low-latency access, such as grant-free mechanisms, can enhance the timeliness of URLLC transmissions. Despite its advancements, URLLC implementation faces numerous challenges, including resource allocation, interference management, and integration with emerging technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML). As networks evolve towards 6G, URLLC is expected to expand its role to support next-generation applications such as holographic communications, immersive extended reality (XR), and the Tactile Internet [3]. These applications will demand even more stringent latency and reliability metrics, driving the need for new innovations in designing URLLC. The continued development of URLLC plays a pivotal role in enabling a hyper-connected, intelligent world, making it a cornerstone of future wireless communication systems.

Achieving sub-millisecond latency and ultra-high reliability necessitates precise coordination across multiple network layers, from the physical layer to application-level processes. For example, advancements in modulation schemes, such as low-density parity-check (LDPC) codes, can improve reliability [4]. Similarly, multi-input multi-output (MIMO) systems have been instrumental in enhancing spectral efficiency and reliability [5]. However, these techniques often come with trade-offs in computational complexity and energy consumption, which are particularly challenging in resource-constrained environments. The transition to 6G networks introduces additional complexities, as URLLC is expected to support even more demanding applications such as immersive XR, autonomous drone swarms, and real-time digital twins [6]. These use cases require the integration of novel paradigms, including reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) for dynamic signal optimization [7]. Furthermore, the incorporation of AI and machine learning techniques can optimize resource allocation and interference management in real-time, but their integration into low-latency systems presents new challenges in terms of computational overhead and model interpretability [8]. Given these complexities, a comprehensive review is necessary to consolidate existing knowledge, identify technological and methodological gaps, and provide a roadmap for future research.

This paper categorizes existing URLLC research across various applications. For instance, URLLC applications in industrial IoT and autonomous vehicles. System-level strategies, such as network slicing, are discussed to evaluate their effects on latency and reliability metrics, particularly in scenarios involving the coexistence of other services [9], [10]. The paper identifies open challenges and future research directions for URLLC as networks transition toward 6G. Challenges such as integrating URLLC with emerging technologies like RIS and AI-driven optimization are explored. This review aims to serve as a foundational reference for researchers, guiding the evolution of URLLC in next-generation networks.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

To present a comprehensive analysis, this review categorizes the existing studies into three primary domains: autonomous vehicles, industrial IoT, and Coexistence of URLLC with different services.

A. URLLC in Autonomous Vehicles Applications

URLLC is pivotal for enabling Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication, which ensures real-time data exchange critical for collision avoidance and autonomous navigation. The study in [11] focuses on the critical role of URLLC in supporting autonomous vehicles by ensuring reliable and low-latency communication within 5G networks. Using Euclidean norm theory, the authors propose a joint reliability and latency evaluation function and illustrate their interaction through Monte Carlo simulations. To enhance URLLC performance, a network slicing solution, extending from resource slicing to service and function slicing, is introduced. The work in [12] explores the integration of 5G-enabled URLLC within LTE-based Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X) infrastructure to ensure fast and secure communication for Connected Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs). The study focuses on road safety applications by leveraging a secure, geo-specific, and localized cooperative driving system. Roadside Units (RSUs) utilize physical layer parameters to generate cryptographic keys for end-to-end communication, while On-Board Unit (OBU) containers provide cryptographic services as microservices in real-time. To optimize latency in the highly dynamic environment of C-V2X, the authors employ zero-forced sparse channel estimation for multimedia broadcast multicast services (eMBMS). The authors of [13] discuss the need for URLLC in V2V communication, focusing on efficient resource slicing mechanisms to ensure transmission reliability and low latency. The authors propose a resource slicing algorithm where the next Generation Node B (gNB) allocates orthogonal Resource Blocks (RBs) to V2V links, mitigating interference and enhancing reliability. The algorithm dynamically updates resource allocation based on the channel state of each V2V link, leveraging reinforcement learning (RL) for adaptive decision-making in dynamic V2V environments.

The work in [14] addresses the need for High Throughput Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication (HT-URLLC) to support future vehicular applications like autonomous and remote driving. A hybrid

network design combining Millimeter-Wave (mmWave) and Sub-6 GHz communications is proposed for V2X networks. The authors introduce a MAC protocol for a linear vehicular network, where vehicles form Lane Clusters (LCs) using directional mmWave antennas for multi-hop data propagation. LC terminals then use Sub-6 GHz omnidirectional antennas to communicate with nearby LCs, RSUs, and cellular base stations. A two-timeslot MAC scheme with schedule alignment and coordination protocols is developed to resolve channel contention and mitigate cross-lane interference. The study in [15] highlights the importance of ultra-reliable and low-latency vehicular communication to support the advanced requirements of intelligent transportation systems in the 6G era. Traditional orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) modulation faces limitations in high-mobility environments due to the significant impact of Doppler shifts. Additionally, dynamic network topologies create difficulties in aligning beams in multi-antenna configurations. To address these issues, the authors propose a novel framework combining orthogonal time frequency space (OTFS) modulation with sensing-assisted predictive beamforming. The OTFS scheme, operating in the delay-Doppler (DD) domain, is designed to enhance communication reliability under vehicular conditions. The sensing-assisted beamforming method reduces latency and overhead by eliminating the reliance on pilot signals for beam alignment. Furthermore, the paper explores the potential of DD channel representation to enable effective channel prediction. The authors conclude by discussing ongoing challenges and future research opportunities in advancing low-latency and reliable vehicular communications. In [16], the authors focus on the critical role of 5G networks in supporting advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS) and their reliance on URLLC as specified in 3GPP Release 16. A major challenge in URLLC implementation is balancing high reliability, characterized by a low block error rate (BLER), with minimal latency in dynamic vehicular environments. The authors propose a Markov Chain model for link adaptation, capable of predicting three key performance indicators (KPIs): end-to-end latency, throughput, and BLER, based on the selected modulation and coding scheme. The study in [17] presents an intelligent resource allocation framework for V2V communications, where the BS assigns orthogonal frequency resources to V2V links. By allocating orthogonal RBs to each link, interference is mitigated, enhancing system reliability compared to non-orthogonal approaches. The framework utilizes Hopfield Neural Networks (HNNs) to design a resource allocation mechanism that considers both the channel state of V2V links and network traffic.

B. URLLC in Industrial IoT Applications

URLLC supports real-time communication between sensors, actuators, and control systems, revolutionizing manufacturing and industrial operations. This paper in [18] examines the integration of 5G networks with the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). The 5G architecture supports IIoT by addressing stringent requirements such as ultra-low latency, real-time processing, high data rates, and reliability, enabling seamless and ubiquitous connectivity. The paper provides an analysis of beyond 5G (B5G) IIoT networks, focusing on eMBB and URLLC services. Additionally, it highlights key enabling technologies, diverse applications, and the critical trade-offs between eMBB and URLLC. The work in [19] presents a framework for mission-critical applications in next-generation (5G and beyond) wireless networks. With billions of connected devices expected to support industry 5.0, applications like smart grids, remote surgery, and intelligent transportation systems demand robust communication solutions. The paper considers an IIoT scenario where a control node (CN) communicates with a target device (TD) using a cooperative device (CD). A transmission protocol is introduced, incorporating nonlinear energy harvesting mechanisms and dual-phase transmissions (direct and cooperative). The network's performance is analyzed in terms of outage probability and BLER under Rayleigh fading channels. The paper in [20] investigates the role of URLLC in supporting delay-sensitive control applications within future wireless networks, particularly in the IIoT. Many industrial devices require real-time, high-frequency control services to enhance operational accuracy and ensure human safety. The paper examines a joint communication and delay-sensitive control (JCDS) system incorporating URLLC, where control intervals are significantly shorter than transmission latency. The control performance, measured by the mean square error (MSE) of plant states, is analyzed

theoretically. The study derives the optimal blocklength for control codewords, data rates, and the minimum required control periods to minimize control latency.

The study in [21] examines uplink transmission in URLLC for IIoT networks, focusing on the impact of channel estimation accuracy on transmission performance and coverage range. The authors aim to optimize the tradeoff between channel training and data transmission overheads in the short blocklength regime. A closed-form approximation of the transmission error probability with imperfect channel state information (CSI) is derived. The study further optimizes the allocation of symbols to channel training and data transmission to maximize the communication range while meeting URLLC quality-of-service (QoS) requirements. Additionally, the influence of spatial diversity on transmission performance and coverage is analyzed. The work in [22] discusses the critical need for secure and energy-efficient URLLC in mission-critical IIoT applications. To enhance communication efficiency, URLLC employs short-packet signals for transmitting delay-sensitive control information among IoT devices. However, the openness of the wireless medium makes URLLC vulnerable to security threats. The authors propose a secure and energy-efficient URLLC signal transmission scheme, focusing on physical-layer security (PLS) to provide low-complexity security solutions for IIoT. An optimization problem is formulated with the aim of maximizing the secure energy efficiency of IIoT systems under constraints such as URLLC QoS, decoding error probability, and eavesdropper intercept probability. Average secrecy throughput is used as a metric to evaluate PLS performance. The problem is solved iteratively by optimizing power allocation, blocklength, and pilot signal length to maximize secrecy throughput and minimize average power allocation. Non-asymptotic closed-form expressions are derived for average secrecy throughput and decoding error probability using the Lagrange multiplier technique and Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions to determine optimal power allocation.

The study in [23] addresses the challenge of providing URLLC IIoT users in remote areas using Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Base Stations (UAV-BSs). To overcome the energy consumption limitations of UAV-BSs, the authors propose an energy-efficient trajectory design and a UAV-BS Multi-Channel Irregular Repetition Slotted-ALOHA (UMC-IRSA) method to adapt the New Radio (NR) frame structure for IIoT users. The UMC-IRSA clusters IIoT nodes based on Mahalanobis distance to optimize energy use. The work in [24] addresses the challenge of enabling URLLC in low-power wide-area networks (LPWANs) with massive connectivity. It introduces autoconfigurable nonorthogonal multiple access (AC-NOMA) based on continuous phase modulation (CPM), where devices autonomously select configurations to optimize connectivity. Using ideal power allocation and phase shaping, AC-NOMA achieves significant improvements in user load and near-capacity performance, even in finite blocklength scenarios. By combining AC-NOMA with slotted ALOHA, the approach enhances throughput compared to power-domain NOMA, even with reduced transmit power and basic error correction schemes like repetition coding. A semi-AC-NOMA variant further boosts throughput with minimal latency increase. The authors of [25] explore the need for precise time synchronization in 5G radio access networks, particularly for machine-type communication in industrial automation, smart grids, and automotive applications. Ultra-tight synchronization is essential for tasks such as real-time isochronous operations, fault localization, and monitoring. The authors propose using the timing advance (TA) mechanism to estimate the time of arrival (TOA) and compensate for propagation delays in synchronization procedures. They analyze the impact of TA binning and the challenges posed by multipath channels, which can reduce estimation accuracy. The study demonstrates that averaging multiple consecutive TA values in static device deployments reduces errors to less than 1 microsecond.

C. Coexistence of URLLC with eMBB

The coexistence problem of URLLC and eMBB traffics has been widely explored in the literature. For instance, the study in [26] investigates the non-orthogonal coexistence of eMBB and URLLC in the downlink of multi-cell massive MIMO systems. A unified framework is proposed, combining infinite-blocklength analysis for eMBB spectral efficiency with finite-blocklength analysis for URLLC error probability using mismatched decoding and saddlepoint approximation. Two coexistence strategies, puncturing

(PUNC) and superposition coding (SPC), are evaluated under statistical CSI at the users, accounting for factors like imperfect CSI, pilot overhead, spatial correlation, and URLLC activation patterns. The work in [27] introduces a distributed learning framework for resource allocation in multi-cell open radio access networks (RANs) supporting URLLC and eMBB services. The proposed framework formulates a resource optimization problem to maximize the average eMBB data rate while meeting URLLC constraints and minimizing data rate variance among eMBB users. A multi-agent Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) algorithm is developed, where network components collaboratively train a global model and distribute learning parameters for execution at the network edge. Specifically, DRL agents at Near-Real-Time Radio Access Network Intelligent Controllers (Near-RT RICs) provide real-time resource allocation decisions, while training occurs offline at Non-Real-Time RICs in regional cloud servers. The paper in [28] addresses the spectrum-sharing challenges between eMBB and URLLC services in 5G networks considering their distinct QoS requirements. The focus is on the co-scheduling problem using puncturing techniques in MIMO NOMA systems. The objective is to maximize the data rate for eMBB users while meeting URLLC latency constraints through joint user selection and power allocation scheduling. An eMBB user clustering mechanism is introduced to balance system throughput and computational complexity. The problem is decomposed into two subproblems: user selection, solved using Gale-Shapley theory, and power allocation, addressed with successive convex approximation (SCA) and difference of convex (DC) programming. An iterative algorithm is proposed to achieve a global solution with low computational complexity.

The authors of [29] discuss the integration of multi-access edge computing (MEC) and 5G networks to support energy-efficient task offloading and scheduling for eMBB and URLLC users. MEC enables mobile devices to offload computational tasks to edge servers, extending battery life and enhancing computational capabilities. The authors formulate the problem as a mixed-integer non-linear optimization model to address task offloading and user scheduling. By decomposing the problem into sub-problems, a block coordinate descent (BCD) algorithm is used to iteratively achieve convergence. The study in [30] examines the performance of orthogonal and non-orthogonal multiple access (OMA and NOMA) for multiplexing eMBB and URLLC users in the uplink of a multi-cell Cloud Radio Access Network (C-RAN). While eMBB users benefit from long codewords distributed over time and frequency, URLLC users require localized, low-latency transmissions decoded at edge nodes (ENs). eMBB traffic, on the other hand, utilizes centralized decoding at the cloud to manage interference. The paper investigates the trade-offs between eMBB and URLLC in terms of eMBB rate and URLLC metrics like rate, access latency, and reliability. It evaluates NOMA strategies, including puncturing and successive interference cancellation (SIC), under various inter-cell interference, signal-to-noise ratio, and fronthaul capacity scenarios. The work in [31] addresses the resource scheduling challenge for URLLC and eMBB traffic in 5G NR networks. The RBs are initially allocated to eMBB users at each time slot based on their channel state and historical average data rates, using a 2-Dimensional Hopfield Neural Network (2D-HNN) model. The energy function of the 2D-HNN is analyzed to solve the RB allocation problem. The joint scheduling of URLLC and eMBB traffic is then formulated as an optimization problem with chance constraints, aiming to maximize eMBB data rates while ensuring URLLC requirements. The chance constraint is simplified into a linear constraint by analyzing the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the stochastic URLLC traffic.

The study in [32] proposes a null-space-based spatial preemptive scheduler for managing the coexistence of URLLC and eMBB traffic in densely populated 5G networks. URLLC requires stringent latency and reliability, while eMBB demands high data rates, making their coexistence on the same spectrum a complex scheduling challenge. The proposed scheduler framework ensures URLLC QoS by leveraging spatial degrees of freedom to provide an interference-free subspace for URLLC traffic, thereby preserving decoding capability with minimal impact on eMBB performance. It optimizes system performance on a user-centric basis, guaranteeing URLLC requirements while maximizing eMBB ergodic capacity. The work in [33] addresses the scheduling challenges of URLLC and eMBB services in 5G networks, where the coexistence of these services necessitates balancing latency, reliability, and spectral efficiency. A puncturing-based coexistence scheme is proposed to manage URLLC and eMBB traffic. The optimization

problem aims to maximize the minimum long-term expected rate of eMBB users while ensuring URLLC requirements are met. The problem is decomposed into two sub-problems: resource allocation for eMBB users, solved using a heuristic algorithm, and resource allocation for URLLC users, addressed with a one-sided matching game. The paper in [34] explores the simultaneous support of URLLC and eMBB services in 5G NR networks for industrial automation. URLLC is prioritized to meet stringent latency and reliability requirements, enabling motion control and synchronous operation for manufacturing machinery, while eMBB supports remote monitoring. Using stochastic geometry and queuing theory, the authors model preemptive priority service at NR BS.

The study in [35] addresses the challenge of downlink resource scheduling for URLLC and eMBB traffic in 5G networks with non-orthogonal slicing. The resource scheduling problem is formulated as a convex optimization problem, aiming to maximize the sum data rates of eMBB users while ensuring URLLC requirements are met. The work in [36] examines the coexistence of eMBB and URLLC services in 5G networks, focusing on resource allocation and scheduling challenges. The strict latency requirements of URLLC traffic necessitate puncturing ongoing eMBB transmissions, potentially reducing eMBB data rates. To address this, the authors propose a resource allocation strategy based on a joint metric that considers the minimum achievable rate of eMBB and optimal placement of URLLC traffic to minimize eMBB performance loss. The proposed metric guides resource allocation for URLLC users within mini-slots, balancing the demands of both service types efficiently. The paper in [37] investigates multi-connectivity as a solution for meeting the stringent reliability requirements of downlink URLLC in 5G systems. Multi-connectivity involves multiple BSs transmitting to a URLLC user by preempting resources allocated to eMBB users. The paper derives expressions for the achievability, defined as the probability that the URLLC user's BLER target is met, for both joint transmission (JT) and orthogonal transmission (OT) modes over frequency-selective channels. A low-complexity algorithm is proposed to optimize the selection of cooperating BSs and modulation and coding schemes (MCSs) to minimize eMBB throughput loss. For time-varying channels with feedback delays, the study introduces a stochastic reliability requirement that improves the probability of meeting BLER targets across URLLC user locations. The authors of [38] address the challenge of resource allocation for URLLC traffic in 5G NR networks, where URLLC is overlaid on ongoing eMBB transmissions via puncturing. The proposed approach introduces a risk-sensitive formulation to balance URLLC reliability and the protection of eMBB users, particularly those with low data rates. Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR) is employed as a risk measure for eMBB, while the URLLC reliability constraint is represented as a chance constraint and relaxed using Markov's inequality. The resource allocation problem is decomposed into subproblems, transformed into convex forms, and solved iteratively until convergence.

The work in [39] evaluates the coexistence of public eMBB and local URLLC factory networks in next-generation wireless systems to support the real-time control and automation required for industrial applications. The analysis focuses on meeting stringent latency and reliability requirements under synchronized and unsynchronized time division duplexing (TDD) deployments, as well as scenarios with and without macro eMBB traffic inside the factory. The study in [40] addresses the energy-efficient joint network selection, sub-carrier allocation, and power control (EEJNSAPC) problem for the coexistence of eMBB and URLLC services in a shared 6G multi-band heterogeneous network (HetNet). A statistical QoS analysis is performed using stochastic geometry. Given the mixed-integer non-convex nature of the EEJNSAPC problem, the study proposes a hybrid deep reinforcement learning (HDRL-EEJNSAPC) algorithm, combining a double dueling deep Q-network and a soft actor-critic, to address the challenge. The paper in [41] explores resource allocation strategies for integrating eMBB and URLLC services in next-generation wireless networks. These services support diverse requirements, from high throughput to strict latency and reliability, for various mission-critical applications. The study reviews techniques such as network slicing, flexible Transmit Time Interval (TTI), scheduling, and distributed or federated learning, along with advanced approaches using Machine Learning (ML), Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). Challenges in resource allocation for eMBB-URLLC coexistence are highlighted, with proposed solutions for optimizing performance in heterogeneous networks.

III. OPEN CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

A. Open Challenges

- Integration with AI and ML:** Developing adaptive and interpretable learning models for real-time resource optimization in dynamic and heterogeneous network environments presents several challenges. One of the primary issues is the computational overhead associated with training and deploying complex AI/ML models in resource-constrained environments, such as mobile edge nodes or IoT devices. These systems often lack the processing power required for real-time inference, necessitating lightweight and efficient model architectures. Additionally, ensuring the scalability of these models to handle large-scale, multi-user deployments with diverse QoS requirements is another significant hurdle. Integration with existing network protocols adds further complexity, as AI-driven solutions must seamlessly interact with traditional communication standards while maintaining compatibility and performance. Moreover, the interpretability of AI/ML models is a pressing concern, particularly in mission-critical applications like autonomous vehicles or industrial automation, where decisions must be explainable and verifiable to ensure reliability and safety. Recent studies, such as [42]–[44], have proposed federated learning frameworks to address these challenges, but substantial gaps remain.
- Resource Allocation:** Addressing the scalability of resource allocation techniques to support dense and diverse deployments without compromising fairness or efficiency remains a critical challenge in URLLC. Dense deployments often involve numerous interconnected devices with varying QoS requirements, which necessitates highly efficient resource allocation frameworks. Techniques such as dynamic spectrum allocation and reinforcement learning-based scheduling algorithms have been proposed to optimize resource distribution in real-time [2], [45], [46]. However, these methods often struggle to balance the competing demands of latency, reliability, and energy efficiency, particularly in heterogeneous environments where traffic patterns and device capabilities vary significantly. Moreover, ensuring fairness across devices without compromising overall network performance adds another layer of complexity. The challenge extends to designing scalable architectures capable of supporting billions of connected devices anticipated in future 6G networks, emphasizing the need for interdisciplinary innovations that combine advanced optimization techniques with robust hardware solutions.
- Interference Management:** Designing cross-layer interference mitigation frameworks to enable seamless coexistence of URLLC with eMBB and mMTC services is a critical challenge in next-generation wireless networks. The inherent differences in service requirements—URLLC demanding ultra-low latency and high reliability, eMBB prioritizing high data rates, and mMTC focusing on massive connectivity—make their coexistence within the same spectrum a non-trivial problem. Interference management is vital to ensure that the stringent requirements of URLLC are not compromised while accommodating the needs of eMBB and mMTC.
- Security and Privacy:** Developing robust encryption protocols and intrusion detection systems tailored to the low-latency and high-reliability demands of URLLC is a critical challenge that requires balancing security with performance constraints. Encryption protocols designed for URLLC must ensure data confidentiality and integrity while introducing minimal latency to meet the stringent timing requirements of mission-critical applications. Traditional cryptographic methods often impose significant computational overhead, making them unsuitable for real-time URLLC systems. Advanced lightweight cryptographic algorithms, such as those based on elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) and quantum-resistant encryption techniques, have been explored to address these issues [47], [48]. Furthermore, intrusion detection systems (IDS) for URLLC need to operate in real-time, identifying and mitigating potential threats without disrupting ongoing communications. ML-based IDS frameworks, which utilize anomaly detection and predictive analysis, have shown promise in proactively identifying security breaches [49]. However, integrating these systems into URLLC environments introduces challenges such as computational complexity, energy efficiency, and compatibility with

existing network protocols. Another pressing issue is the protection of sensitive data in heterogeneous networks, where URLLC must coexist with other communication services.

- **Cost and Scalability:** Exploring cost-effective solutions for deploying URLLC in rural and remote areas involves overcoming unique challenges such as limited infrastructure, high deployment costs, and energy constraints. Lightweight algorithms designed for low computational overhead play a pivotal role in ensuring that URLLC can operate effectively on resource-constrained devices commonly found in these regions. Additionally, energy-efficient hardware solutions, such as low-power base stations and solar-powered communication nodes, are being developed to reduce operational costs while ensuring sustainable connectivity. Another critical aspect is the integration of non-terrestrial networks (NTNs), such as satellites and UAVs, to extend URLLC coverage to underserved areas. Furthermore, network slicing techniques tailored for rural deployments prioritize essential services such as emergency communications and telemedicine, ensuring that the most critical applications receive the required bandwidth and reliability. Edge computing frameworks are also being adapted to minimize latency in rural areas. By deploying micro-data centers at the edge of the network, computational tasks can be processed closer to the users, reducing the need for long-haul communication and enhancing the responsiveness of URLLC applications. Despite these advancements, achieving cost-effective solutions for large-scale rural deployments requires ongoing collaboration across various fields to develop scalable, adaptable, and affordable approaches tailored to the unique challenges of these environments.

B. Future Directions

The future of URLLC lies in addressing its current challenges while exploring innovative solutions to meet the demands of next-generation wireless networks. As 5G networks evolve and 6G begins to take shape, the integration of emerging technologies such as quantum communication, RIS, and AI will play a pivotal role in transforming URLLC into a cornerstone of hyper-connected systems. Moreover, extending the reach of URLLC to underserved regions and new application domains, such as autonomous systems in remote environments or real-time analytics in healthcare, presents significant opportunities and challenges. In the following, we discuss some of the potential future directions:

- **Quantum Communication:** Quantum communication technologies hold immense promise for achieving unparalleled levels of security and latency performance in URLLC networks. Quantum key distribution (QKD) enables the exchange of encryption keys with theoretically unbreakable security, making it highly suitable for mission-critical applications. Additionally, quantum entanglement can potentially facilitate near-instantaneous data transfer, addressing latency bottlenecks in current systems. However, implementing quantum communication on a large scale requires overcoming significant challenges, including maintaining quantum coherence over long distances and developing cost-effective quantum hardware. Future research must also investigate hybrid models that integrate quantum communication with classical networks for a seamless transition.
- **Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces:** RIS represents a promising avenue for enhancing signal reliability and reducing energy consumption in URLLC scenarios. RIS involves programmable surfaces that can manipulate electromagnetic waves to improve signal strength, coverage, and reliability. This technology is particularly advantageous in dense urban environments, where traditional line-of-sight communication is often obstructed. Future research should focus on optimizing RIS design for low-cost manufacturing and real-time adaptability to dynamic network conditions.
- **Non-Terrestrial Networks:** NTNs, including satellite and UAV-based communication systems, are essential for extending URLLC coverage to underserved and remote areas. NTNs offer a scalable solution to bridge the connectivity gap, particularly in regions where terrestrial networks are economically unfeasible. Key challenges include minimizing latency in satellite communication and ensuring seamless handover between terrestrial and non-terrestrial systems. Advanced routing algorithms and

resource management strategies will be critical to realizing the full potential of NTN in supporting URLLC.

- **AI-Driven Network Optimization:** The integration of AI with URLLC offers transformative opportunities to enhance network performance, resource allocation, and fault detection. AI algorithms can analyze real-time network data to predict traffic patterns, optimize resource utilization, and preemptively address potential disruptions. However, challenges such as computational overhead, model scalability, and explainability remain significant barriers to widespread adoption. Future research should prioritize the development of lightweight AI models and federated learning approaches that balance performance with privacy and efficiency.
- **Interdisciplinary Approaches:** The future of URLLC lies in interdisciplinary collaboration that combines advances in AI, networking, and hardware design. For example, the integration of energy-efficient hardware with AI-driven software solutions can create holistic frameworks that address the multifaceted demands of next-generation networks. Similarly, partnerships between academia and industry will be crucial for translating theoretical innovations into practical implementations.

IV. CONCLUSION

This review has highlighted the remarkable advancements achieved in the field of URLLC, alongside the persistent challenges that require attention to achieve its full potential. The paper discussed existing works on URLLC applications and their trade-offs, including latency, reliability, scalability, and energy efficiency. It serves as a foundational reference for researchers seeking to address the unique demands of next-generation wireless networks. The insights presented in this review highlight the transformative role of URLLC in enabling critical applications across diverse sectors such as autonomous vehicles, industrial automation, telemedicine, and beyond. Despite these advancements, several gaps remain, including resource allocation, interference management, and the integration of emerging technologies such as AI, quantum communication, and RIS. Addressing these challenges requires interdisciplinary collaboration, innovative solutions, and sustained research efforts.

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